

FRANSUZ TILIDA “YOSH DAVR”LARINING LEKSIK-SEMANTIK TASNIFI

Axrorova Ruzixon Usmonovna

f.f.f.d., dotsent

axrorova.prof@gmail.com

Pazilova Shukura Maxamadovna

Linvistika (fransuz tili) II-bosqich magistranti

ANNOTATSIYA

Mazkur maqolada inson yosh davrining fransuz tilida leksik-semantik tasnifi va lingvistik jihatdan qilingan ba'zi tahlillar, fikr va mulohazalar qisqacha yoritib berilgan bo'lib, unda «yosh davr»lari fransuz tilida o'z ifodasini topgan. “Yosh davr”lari tushunchasi tilda turli xil leksik vositalar orqali verballashadi. Boshqa tomondan esa “yosh davr”lari semantikasiga ega bo'lgan so'zlar ko'chma ma'nolarda ham verballashadi. “Yosh davr” semantikasi, shuningdek, so'z yasaliş darajasida ham o'z ifodasini topadi haqida ma'lumotlar berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: *yosh davrlari, leksik vositalar, seminal tasvirlar, yosh guruhlari, yosh, yosh, madaniy-tarixiy, ijtimoiy, semiotik, omillar, konkret tizim, til manzarasi, til, lotin, yosh nominatsiyalari, qo'llanish me'yorlari, jamiyat, yosh tarkibi, xususiyat, yoshlik, qarilik, ijobiy, salbiy baho, milliy-madaniy.marasmus, aqliy faoliyat, jismoniy faollik, qarilik, surunkali, bolalik, leksema.*

ANNOTATION

In this article, the lexical-semantic classification of human youth in the French language and some analyzes, opinions and comments made from a linguistic point of view are briefly explained, in which the "youth period" is expressed in the French language. The concept of "ages" is verbalized in the language through various lexical means. On the other hand, words with the semantics of "young age" are also verbalized in figurative meanings. It is reported that the semantics of the "young age" is also expressed at the level of word formation.

Keywords: *age periods, lexical tools, seminal images, age groups, age, age, cultural-historical, social, semiotic, factors, concrete system, language landscape, language, Latin, age nominations, usage norms, society, age structure, characteristic, youth, old age, positive, negative evaluation, national-cultural.marasmus, mental activity, physical activity, old age, chronic, childhood, lexeme.*

KIRISH

“Yosh davr”lari tushunchasi tilda turli xil leksik vositalar orqali verballashadi. Boshqa tomondan esa “yosh davr”lari semantikasiga ega bo‘lgan so‘zlar ko‘chma ma‘nolarda ham verballashadi. “Yosh davr” semantikasi, shuningdek, so‘z yasaliş darajasida ham o‘z ifodasini topadi [Akhrorova R., 2023:187].

“Yosh davr”larining ma‘nolari, albatta, semali tasavvurlarga egadir. Masalan, so‘rg‘ich so‘zining lug‘aviy talqinlarida so‘rg‘ich, chaqaloq bolalar uchun mo‘ljallanishiga ishora qilinadi [Akhrorova R., 2022:167].

Marazm so‘zining bosh mazmuni ruscha-o‘zbekcha lug‘atda quyidagicha talqin qilinadi. Odamning psixik va jismoniy faoliyati qarilik yoki uzoq vakt davom etadigan surunkali kasallik tufayli kuch-quvvatdan qolish, ma‘naviy tushkunlik kuzatiladigan holat [Akhrorova R., 202:179].

ADABIYOTLAR TAHLILI VA METODOLOGIYA

Frantsuz tili izohli lug‘atlarida mavjud bo‘lgan “yosh davr”larining nomlari, ya‘ni asosiy “yosh davr”larining nomlari bo‘lmish leksemalar quyidagicha keltirildi.

“Yosh davr”lari va ularning lug‘aviy definititsiyalari

Fransuz tilida:

Enfance-“болалик”

1. *Periode de la vie l'être humain qui va de la naissance jusqu'à l'âge de la puberté. Une enfance très malheureuse.*

2. *L'enfance ; les enfants. La cruauté de l'enfance.*

3. *Fig. Debut, commencement, premier temps. L'enfance du monde. Loc.fam.*

C'est l'enfance de l'art; c'est très facile à faire [*Petit Robert, 1997 : 2388*].

Adolescence

ge compris entre la puberté et l'âge adulte.

Jeunesse.

1. *Parti de la vie comprise entre l'enfance et l'âge adulte. La première jeunesse; adolescence. Il faut que jeunesse se passé (Prov.)*

2. *Il faut être indulgent pour les fautes dues à la vivacité à l'inexpérience des jeunes gens.*

3. *(Animaux, plantes, choses). Jeune âge. La jeunesse du monde.*

4. *Ensemble des personnes jeunes.- Si jeunesse savait, si vieillesse pouvait; si la jeunesse avait (Prov.); l'expérience et la vieillesse la force.- La jeunesse dorée. (Loc).*

5. *Fraicheur, vigueur. Une oeuvre pleine de jeunesse [Petit Robert, 1997 : 2388].*

“Maturité” - етуклик

1. *Etat de ce qui est mûr. Fruit à maturité.*

2. *Epoque, entre la jeunesse et la vieillesse, ou l'être humain atteint la plénitude de son développement physique et intellectuel//Fig. Plénitude qui est l'aboutissement d'une évolution. Ses dons artistiques sont arrivés à maturité.*

3. *Prudence, sagesse c'est qui vient avec l'âge et l'expérience.*

(Suisse) *Diplôme qui couronne les études secondaires, baccalauréat* [Petit Robert, 1997 : 2388].

Vieillesse

1. *Period ultime de la vie. Avoir une vieillesse heureuse.*

2. *Fait d'être âgé. Mourir de vieillesse.*

3. (Sing. collectif.) *Les personnes âgées. Caisse de retraite pour la vieillesse pouvait* [Petit Robert, 1997 : 2387].

NATIJARLAR

Shunday qilib, frantsuz tilida to'rtta asosiy “yosh davr”lari ajratiladi. Asosiy farq frantsuz tilining izohli lug'atlarida o'smirlik (adolescence) davrining yoshlik (jeunesse) davriga kiritilgan.

“Yosh davr”larining asosiy xususiyatlari haqidagi ko'p jihatlardan bir biriga o'xshaydigan tushuncha-tasavvur frantsuz tili izohli lug'atlaridagi maqollarda aks ettirilgan. Masalan, bolalik bilan birorta ishda sinalmaganlik, kasb mahoratining yo'qligi assotsiativ bog'lanadi (frantsuz tilidagi s'est l'enfance de l'art (bu san'atning bolaligi iborasi). Yoshlik davri uchun hushyorlik, tezkorlik, serharakatlik, qiziqqonlik, jo'shqinlik, tezboblik, (vivacité) ya'ni, muvofiq tarzda frantsuz tilidagi tajribasizlik, inexperience, tozalik, froucheur kuch, quvvat, tetiklik, frantsuz tilidagi vigueur so'zlariga lug'aviy jihatdan ekvivalentdirlar.

MUHOKAMA

Shuningdek yetuklik davriga ehtiyotkorlik - prudence, donolik - sagesse, tajribalilik - experience fazilatlarini xosdir. Qarilik esa hayotiy kuch-quvvat yetishmasligi, bo'shashganlik bilan assotsiativ bog'lanadi, (masalan: si jeunesse savait, si vieillesse pouvait).

Shunday qilib, frantsuz lisoniy ongi uchun eng ahamiyatlilari deb, bolalik, yoshlik, yetuklik va qarilik “yosh davr”lari e'tirof etiladi [Akhrorova R., 2022:108].

XULOSA

“Yosh davr”ining asosiy tushunchasi mazmuni haqidagi tasavvurni “yosh” haqidagi boshqa birliklarning lisoniy ma'nolarini, ularning so'zni tashkil etuvchi aloqalarini, assotsiativ lug'atlarni, tarkibiga “yosh davr”larining nomlanishlari kiradigan paremiyalarni tahlil qilish orqali to'ldirish mumkin.

ADABIYOTLAR

1. Akhrorova Ruzikhon Usmonovna. LEXICAL-SEMANTIC EXPRESSION OF EARLY YOUTH/JEUNESSE IN FRENCH. International scientific and practical in "MODERN PHILOLOGICAL PARADIGMS: INTERACTION OF TRADITIONS AND INNOVATIONS II". 2022/4/5. – P.166-168.
2. Akhrorova Ruzikhon Usmonovna. Naming of the “age” concept. SCIENCE AND INNOVATION INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL. 2022/10/20. –P. 178-182.
3. Akhrorova Ruzikhon Usmonovna. Essay writing terms. Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies. 2022/12/22. –P. 107-109.
4. Akhrorova Ruzikhon Usmanovna. “Yosh tushunchasi lingvistik talqini”. Innovative Development in Educational Activities, 2023. B.187-190.
5. Ahrorova, R. U. (2021). SEMANTIC ANALYSIS OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS REPRESENTING “YOUTH” IN FRENCH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES. Theoretical & Applied Science, (7), 122-126.
6. AKHROROVA, R. U. (2021). THE LINGUISTIC IMAGE OF THE WORLD AND THE GENDER ASPECT OF THE CONCEPT OF" AGE" IN FRENCH AND UZBEK. THEORETICAL & APPLIED SCIENCE Учредители: Теоретическая и прикладная наука, (9), 585-589.
7. *Le Nouveau Petit Robert*. Dictionnaire alphabétique et analogique de la langue française // texte remanié et amplifié sous la direction de Josette Rey-Deboie et Alain Rey. – Paris: Dictionnaires Le Robert, 1997. – 2387 p. (PR).
8. *Le Nouveau Petit Robert*. Dictionnaire alphabétique et analogique de la langue française // texte remanié et amplifié sous la direction de Josette Rey-Deboie et Alain Rey. – Paris: Dictionnaires Le Robert, 1997. – 2388 p. (PR).
9. . I.T. Dehqonov (2022). Nutqiy etiket birliklari (fransuz va o‘zbek tillari misolida). Ijodkor o‘qituvchi. 2(23), 222-226.
10. Dehqonov Islom Teshayevich (2022). Uzbek and french speech etiquette units. Journalnx-a multidisciplinary peer reviewed journal. 12(12), 61-64.
11. I.T. Dehqonov (2023). Fransuz etiket qoidalari. O‘ZBEKISTONDA FANLARARO INNOVATSIYALAR VA ILMIY TADQIQOTLAR JURNALI. 17(3), 154-158.
12. Dehqonov Islom Teshayevich, Fozilov Raxmatullo Feruz o‘g‘li (2023). FRANSUZ TILI DATSLARIDA O‘YINLARDAN FOYDALANISH. FORMATION OF PSYCHOLOGY AND PEDAGOGY AS INTERDISCIPLINARY SCIENCES. INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC ONLINE CONFERENCE. In Italy.18, 33-36.

13. Dehqonov Islom Teshayevich, Rahmonova Gulchiroy Yoqubjon qizi (2023). Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida chet tillarini o'qitishda leksik o'yinlardan foydalanish. TURKEY international scientific online conference. "THEORY AND ANALYTICAL ASPECTS OF RECENT RESEARCH".14. 143-147.

14. I.T. Dehqonov, Raymberdiyeva Shahlo Dilshodjon qizi (2023). CHET TILLARINI O'QITISH JARAYONIDA LEKSIK KO'NIKMALARNING O'RNI. MODELS AND METHODS FOR INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF INNOVATIVE RESEACH. In Germany. 22. 211-214

15. Dehqonov Islom Teshayevich (2023) LE PROBLÈME DE LA CORRECTION DU DISCOURS ORAL DES ÉCOLIERS AU STADE INTERMÉDIAIRE DE L'ÉDUCATION. International Journal of Education, Social Science & Humanities. Finland Academic Research Science Publishers. 11(4), 1075-1081.

16. Jo'rayeva, S. (2021, April). HISTORICAL DATES AS THE CONTENT OF VICTOR HUGO'S BIBIMARYAM TEMPLE. In Конференции.

17. Jurayeva, S., & Gofforova, M. (2022). APPLICATION OF PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGE. Models and methods in modern science, 1(17), 16-19.

18. Jurayeva, S., & Haydaraliyev, A. (2022). EXPRESSION OF PROVERBS IN FOREIGN LANGUAGES AND THEIR SPECIFIC CHARACTERISTICS. Models and methods in modern science, 1(17), 8-11.

19. Khusanboevna, J. S. (2022, October). THE THEME OF A HERO IN UZBEK PRODUCTION. In Proceedings of International Educators Conference (Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 28-31).

20. G'aniyevna, S. A. (2023). ISSUES OF INTERCULTURAL COMMUNICATION AND RECEPTION. IJODKOR O'QITUVCHI, 3(28), 191-195.

21. Zinatullina A.X., FRANSUZ VA O'ZBEK TILLARIDA MURAKKAB GAPLARDA ZAMON QO'LLANILISHINING O'ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLARI, IQRO JURNALI / 2023, VOL-2 ISSUE-1, E-ISSN : 2181-4341.

22. Zinatullina A. H, The Word Order within the Complex Sentences of French and Uzbek Languages, Universal journal on innovative education, Volume 2 Issue 3, Year 2023, pages 20-21-22.